

INVESTIGATING THE REFRACTORY PROPERTIES OF UGBAWKA CLAY DEPOSIT FOR INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

Study on the refractory properties of Ugbawka clay deposit for industrial applications has been carried out. Chemical analysis tests were conducted using X-ray fluorescence technique (XRF). The physical properties tests such as shrinkage, porosity, water absorption, modulus of rupture, refractoriness, moisture content, plasticity, thermal shock resistance, cold crushing strength, bulk density, apparent density and modulus of plasticity were carried out using international accepted standard techniques. The results of the chemical analysis showed that the Ugbawka clay has silica SiO₂ (51.2%), alumina Al₂O₃ (28.00%), calcium oxide CaO (2.04%), sodium oxide Na₂O (1.85%) and potassium oxide K₂O (1.85%) as its predominant oxides. The results of the physical properties tests conducted were shrinkage (7.45%) apparent porosity (20.60%), apparent density (2.53%), bulk density (1.90%), water absorption (17.03%), modulus of rupture (30.90/cm²) and cold crushing strength (310.60KN/m²) at 12000C with an estimated refractoriness of 15700C. The clay therefore could be used for the production of alumino-silicate refractory for lining of furnaces for non-ferrous metals, steel making furnaces, kilns soaking and heat-treatment furnaces.

INTRODUCTION

Clay material is a naturally occurring fine-grained earth material made primarily of tiny mineral particles formed from the breakdown of rocks over long period of time. Clay mainly contains clay mineral like kaolinite, illite and montmorillonite, small amount of silica, alumina and water. Clays are naturally occurring materials composed of fine grained minerals with particle size less than 2 microns. When mixed with water, it becomes plastic and hardens when dried or fired (Guggenheim and Martin, 1995). It consists of hydrous aluminosilicate minerals which are arranged in well-ordered patterns comprising of octahedral and tetrahedral geometry which results in packed layers and sheets Olamide et al., (2014).

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Clay minerals are fine-grain materials that acquire plasticity on being mixed with limited quantity of water. They geologically occur as particles with a phyllosilicate or sheet structure with diameters ranging from few microns to a few hundreds of microns. Clay occurs mostly in nature in solids, sediments, sedimentary rocks, hydrothermal densities and are abundantly in every part of Nigeria. Velde (1992) used the swelling property of clay to broadly classify all clays into swelling and non-swelling type.

Clay is natural raw material for many industrial finished products (Chester, 1973) such as refractories, ceramic wares, electrical porcelain insulators etc. Refractoriness are specifically used to conserve heat within a system (Chester, 1973). These refractory materials are employed in constructing furnaces for smelting ores, holding of molten metals and slags, heat treatment operations, kilns for cement production, rotary furnaces for iron ore reduction, cast iron and non-ferrous metals production, glass melting heat exchangers etc.

Refractory material are materials capable of withstanding high temperatures, and that high quality refractory materials that resist high temperature fluctuations between 1000⁰C and 1500⁰C and are also good thermal and electrical insulators (Ameh and Obasi, 2012). Clay is a type of fine-grained natural soil material containing clay minerals. Clays develop plasticity when wet due to a molecular film of water surrounding the clay particles, but become hard, brittle and non-plastic upon drying or firing. Refractoriness are composed of thermally stable mineral aggregate, which are inorganic and nonmetallic (Hassan et al., 2019). Refractoriness belong to the category of ceramic materials, which are utilized for prime temperature typically higher than 1100⁰C (Hassan S. B. 2005). Most refractories are made from naturally occurring high melting point oxides such as SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Cr₂O₃, ZrO (Jack, et al., 2013).

Refractoriness are mostly made up of inorganic compounds which are usually derived from clay. It is characterized by the ability to withstand physical, chemical and corrosive attack without deterioration at elevated temperatures (Musa et al., 2012). These materials are mostly used in Metallurgical industries for the linings of internal furnaces well, melting holding and transportation of metal and slag.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHOD

The raw material (clay) used in this research work was sourced from Ugwaka located at Nkanu East Local Government Area of Ebonyi State of Nigeria. The clay sample was collected from four different locations of the deposits and blended together by pounding process. The chemical analysis was carried out using X-ray fluorescence (XRF). The physical analysis was carried out using international accepted standard.

2.1 Sample preparation for physical analysis

The samples (clay) used for the analysis was sieved, measured and soaked in a calculated amount of water, then stirred vigorously in order to bring it to plastic state. It was allowed to dry for 50 mins for the suspended particles decanted. The sample was allowed to dewater for 5 days after which it was oven dried for 6hours for proper processing.

Plasticity and plasticity ratio

Five (5) specimen were produced using cylindrical mould and a plastomer was used in deforming them.

$$\text{Modulus of plasticity} = \frac{h_1}{y_1}$$

$$\text{Plasticity ratio} = \frac{h_2}{y_2}$$

Where h_1 = original height of deforming load

y_1 = deformed height of load

h_2 = original height of sample

y_2 = deformed height of sample

Moisture content: Five cylindrical specimens (1.5cm dia. x 10cm length) were weighed green and their weight noted. They were then dried in air for two weeks and later oven dried at a temperature of 110⁰C for twenty-four hours. The dry weight of the specimen was measured and recorded.

$$\text{Moisture content} = \frac{W_w - d_w}{W_w} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where W_w = wet weight

d_w = dry weight

Green, Dry and Fired Strength; five rectangular specimens (1.5 x 3.5cm) were taken and recorded. They were oven dried for two days and a rupture testing machine was used to test for the strength at given, dry and fired state. The fired strength was tested after firing the specimens to temperatures of 900⁰C, 1000⁰C, 1100⁰C, 1200⁰C and 1300⁰C respectively.

$$\text{modulus of repture: } \frac{3pl}{2bh} \text{ or } \frac{8pl}{\pi d^2}$$

Where: p = applied load (kg)

I = distance between supports constant (cm)

b = width of the specimen at the point of rupture (cm)

h = height of the specimen at the point of rupture

d = diameter of the cylindrical specimen

Apparent porosity, water absorption, apparent and bulk density tests. Rectangular specimens (5cm x 7cm) were prepared and their weight recorded. They were dried for two weeks, oven dried and their new weight recorded. They were fired to temperatures of 900⁰C, 1000⁰C, 1100⁰C, 1200⁰C and 1300⁰C respectively. Their weights at each stage of firing were recorded. The fired specimens were soaked in water for twenty-four hours and the weight taken and recorded. They were calculated as follows:

$$\text{Apparent porosity} = \frac{S_w - F_w}{S_w - S_{sw}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

$$\text{Water absorption} = \frac{S_{sw} - F_w}{F_w} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

$$\text{Apparent density} = \frac{F_w}{F_w - S_{sw}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{F_w - dw}{S_w - S_{sw}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where S_w = soaked weight

F_w = Fired weight

S_{sw} = Suspended weight

dw = Density of water

Linear dry and fired shrinkage: Rectangular specimen (5cm x 7cm) were produced and marked 5cm lengths. Temperatures of heating ranges was inscribed on the specimens to be fired. They were dried in air for two weeks and oven dried for forty hours. The change in the 5cm length mark was measured. They were then fired to temperatures of 900⁰C, 1000⁰C, 1100⁰C, 1200⁰C and 1300⁰C respectively.

$$a. \text{ Dry Shrinkage (\%)} = \frac{wl - dl}{wl} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

$$b. \text{ Fired Shrinkage (\%)} = \frac{wl - fl}{dl} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where wl = wet length (cm)

dl = dry length (cm)

fl = fired length (cm)

Permeability: Five specimens were prepared using standard specifications of 5.08cm diameter and 5.08cm length/height. They were dried in air for two twenty hours and oven dried for ten hours. Permeability meter was filled with 2000cm³ of water in a bel jar put in place. The orifice was opened and then taken for 2000cm³ of water to displace equal volume of air through the specimen taken. The pressure difference was measured using manometer.

$$p = \frac{vxh}{pxAxt} \text{ or } \frac{vh}{pAt}$$

Where p = permeability meter

V = volume of air passed through the specimen (cm²)

h = height of specimen

A = cross-sectional area of the specimen

p = pressure head under which the air has passed

t = time of flow in seconds

$$\text{or } p = \frac{30072}{pxt} \text{ or } \frac{30072}{pt}$$

Thermal shock resistance: The test was carried out using 50mm x 50mm specimens. They were inserted into a muffle furnace and heated to 900⁰C and held for 15 minutes. They were removed quickly from the furnace, and placed on fire bricks and allowed to cool for fifteen minutes, after the 15 minutes cooling, they were then returned to the furnace and the process repeated for 30 cycles. They were seen at the end of the 30 cycle not to have deformed.

Refractoriness: Pyrometric cone equivalent test was used to determine refractoriness specimen with 50mm pyramid height and 15mm rectangular base were used. They were put inside a refractory plague with two Seeger cone of 12 and 13 and oven dried at 110⁰C. The temperature equivalents for the two Seeger cones were 1340⁰C and 1348⁰C respectively. They were put in a furnace and temperature raised at the rate of 100⁰C per minute until the two Seeger cones bent over level with the base. Upon observation, it was noted that the specimen had not deformed or let alone melting. The firing was continued until temperature of 1400⁰C was attained, yet the specimen remained undeformed.

The refractoriness was estimated using Shuen's formular.

$$\text{refractoriness, } K(^{\circ}C) = \frac{360 + Al_2O_3 - RO}{0.228}$$

Where, Al_2O_3 = % alumina in the clay

RO = sum of all other oxides besides silica

360, 0.228 = constants.

Cold crushing strength (C.C.S.): Test pieces measuring 50 x 30 x 30mm were prepared and air-dried for 48 hours after which they were transferred to a furnace and heated for a period of 5 hours and at a temperature of 1100⁰C. After the heating process, samples were removed and allowed to cool at room temperature and each piece was placed in a crusher. During test, the pressure adding surface was adequately aligned to the centre of

the spherical seat of the equipment. Load was applied axially and continually until the test piece fractured. The procedure was repeated for other test pieces. The respective loads at which each test piece fractured were recorded. The cold crushing strength (CSS) was calculated from the equation.

$$CCS = \frac{F}{A} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where A = Area of test specimen

F = Applied load

Loss on ignition: 50g of the clay sample was oven dried 110⁰C and cooled in a desiccator. The dried sample was put inside the crucible and the weight of the crucible and the sample were recorded (m²). The crucible with its contents were cooled in a desiccator and then re-weighed (m³)

3.0 Results and Discussion

The results of this research were presented in Table 3.1 – 3.3 and Fig. 3.1 – 3.....

The result of the chemical analysis was determined using X-ray florecense. The results of the chemical compositions were presented in table 3.1, from the table 3.1 it was shown that Ugbawka clay has silica 51.2% (SiO₂), 28.0% Al₂O₃ and 1.85% (Na₂O) as its predominant oxides with TiO₂ and MnO as traced oxides. The alumina and silica contents of 28.0% and 51.2% fall within the range of a high duty fire clay refractories of 25 – 38% Al₂O₃ and 57 – 70% SiO₂ respectively. The percentages of most of the oxides tested especially Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ falls within the specific standard (Odo et al., 2009).

The results of the physical properties of Ugbawka clay deposit were shown in Tables 3.2 – 3.3. From the Table 3.2, and Figures 3.1 and 3.2. It was observed tthat shrinkage modulus of rupture, cold crushing strength (CCS) increased with increase in firing temperature, while apparent porosity, apparent density, water of absorption of Ugbawka clay, deposit decreased with increase in firing temperature. The higher a clay mineral is fired, the more it losses its absorbed moisture and constitutional water thereby increases the shrinkage and reduces porosity. From Table 3.3, it was shown that Ugbawka Clay has modulus of plasticity (4.60), thermal shock resistance (29 cycles) and moisture content (5.03%). From the table 3.2 and 3.3, it was observed that the physical properties of Ugbawka clay determined, fell within the international standard organization (ISO) specifications for alumina-silicate refractories of the fire clay (Ugwoke and Amalu, 2017). The estimated refractoriness of the Ugbawka clay sample was determined using Shuen’s formular. The estimated refractoriness of the clay sample is in accordance with the pyrometric cone of 31. The estimated refractoriness of the clay (1570⁰C) fell within the acceptable standard range of 1500 – 1700⁰C for fire clay refractory materials (Agbo, et al., 2015). The sintering point of above 1500⁰C is a good indication that Ugbawka Clay deposit. Is of high refractory class and can be used where medium and high temperatures are required for melting of non-ferrous metal, and their alloys, treatment of steel and their alloys.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The clay is aluminosilicate refractory clay of high fire-clay class. The chemical compositions of the clay were compared favourably with the compositions of other clays that are used for specified industrial applications. The clay could therefore, be used in the production of alumino-silicate refractory for lining of furnace for non-ferrous metals, steel making furnances for non-ferrous metals, steelmaking furnances, kilns soaking pits and heal treatment furnances.

Table 3.1: Chemical Composition of Ugbawka Clay deposit

Constituent	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	MnO	K ₂ O	MgO	CaO	Na ₂ O
Percentage	51.2	28.0	1.12	1.62	1.53	2.34	1.85
Constituent	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	MnO	V ₂ O ₅	AgO		
Percentage	0.56	0.04	0.40	0.17	0.97		

Table 3.1b: Chemical composition of refractory clays by International Standard

Constituent	Fired clay (%)	Refractory bricks (%)
SiO ₂	55 – 75	51-70
Al ₂ O ₃	25 – 45	25-40
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.5 – 2.0	0.5 – 2.4
K ₂ O	<2.0	
MgO	<2.0	
LiO	12-15	

Source: Gupta (2008)

Table 3.2: Physical Properties tests of Ugbawka clay deposit tested at 900^oC, 1000^oC, 1100^oC, 1200^oC and 1300^oC were:

Temperature ^o C	900 ^o C	1000 ^o C	1100 ^o C	1200 ^o C	1300 ^o C
Wet-dry shrinkage %	4.30	4.40	4.53	4.58	4.00
Dry-fired shrinkage (%)	2.18	2.38	2.64	2.87	3.00
Total shrinkage %	6.48	6.78	7.17	7.45	7.00
Apparent porosity (%)	33.16	31.50	28.10	23.20	20.60
Apparent density (g/cm ³)	3.21	3.10	2.90	2.72	2.53
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.94	1.86	1.88	1.89	1.90
Water absorption (%)	26.72	23.40	21.30	18.00	17.03
Modulus of Rupture (MOR) kg/m ²	22.60	24.70	27.20	29.40	30.90
Cold crushing strength (CCS) KN/mm ²	225.00	235.11	250.12	274.50	310.60

Table 3.3: Other physical properties of Ugbawka Clay deposit tested

Property	Value
Modulus of plasticity	4.60
Thermal shock resistance (cycles)	29
Green strength (kgf/cm ²)	28.10
Moisture content %	5.03
Permeability (No)	56.20
Sintering point (^o C)	>1400 ^o C
Refractoriness	1570 ^o C

Table 3.3b: Physical properties and Thermal properties of International standard

Properties	Value
Fired linear shrinkage (%)	2-10
Permeability to air	25-90
Apparent density (g/cm ³)	20-30

Bulk density (g/cm^2)	2.2-2.80
Cold Crushing strength MPa	15.0 minimum
Thermal shock Resistance, cycles	20-30
Refractoriness $^{\circ}\text{C}$	1500 - 1750
Moisture content, %	1-13

Source: Chester (1973)

Figure 3.1: Relationship between Water Absorption and Modulus of Rupture on refractory properties of Ugbawka clay.

Figure 3.2: Relationship of Total Shrinkage, Apparent density and Bulk density on the refractory properties of Ugbawka clay.

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